

Social Entrepreneurship Education: A systematic review of curricula contents and teaching methods

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Abstract:

Social entrepreneurship education is one of the fastest-growing subject areas in the world. Despite these developments, scholars and practitioners are far from reaching a consensus about "what" and "how" to educate social entrepreneurship. This study presents a systematic review of 30 articles published in Scopus and web of science databases between 2007 to January 2020. It offers an overview of the most popular SE courses and teaching methods on social entrepreneurship education programs. Based on identified research gaps, we provide future research directions that will help more researchers and practitioners conceptualize social entrepreneurship education.

Keywords: Social entrepreneurship education, SE courses, teaching methods, entrepreneurship education, Social entrepreneurship.

1. Introduction

There is widespread agreement that entrepreneurial activity is a critical component of a country's economic and social growth. This practice has been ever more acute in recent years, as it has been recognized as an essential tool for wealth creation, which allows for an increase in job rates^[1]. The same holds with social entrepreneurship. The focus here is on the social value created by such entrepreneurs and their role in opening up new paths to resolve major social improvement issues, mainly for the benefit of the marginalized and disadvantaged.

Many entrepreneurs likely have innate capacities that will enable them to deal with the world's challenges, both structural and relational. However, there is only one way to reinforce those abilities for those who already have them and those who do not. This mechanism is called education and training^[2]. Education is a lifelong process designed to develop individuals' essential qualities and build on new skills. In effect, there was an agreement that entrepreneurship education and training play a crucial role in the predisposition to undertake^[3,4]. There seems to be a correlation between the educational level and the enterprising pace, and there are indications that higher rates of education will lead to a higher level of entrepreneurship (GEM, 2012; GEM Special Report, 2008; High Impact Entrepreneurship Global Report, 2011).

However, entrepreneurship education can play a vital role in creating more and/or more capable entrepreneurs^[5,6]. The same is true with social entrepreneurship. Social entrepreneurship education (SEE) is critical to the growth of both people and societies. It is possible to grow individuals' social understanding, innovation, and openness to societal challenges by delivering social entrepreneurship education. Consequently, social entrepreneurship education facilitates social problem-solving in society, raises social welfare, and leads to a sustainable national economy^[2].

A growing number of social entrepreneurship centers have been founded at universities worldwide in the last decade. Despite these developments, scholars and practitioners are far from reaching a consensus about "what" and "how" to educate social entrepreneurship. We conducted a review of articles on SEE published during 2007– January 2020, analyzed by using "Nvivo" software.

This paper aimed to map the most popular SEE contents and teaching methods to provide a clearer picture and introduce new pathways and perspectives to the field of social

entrepreneurship education. In response, we formulated the following research questions: what different SE content in universities, and how this course offered? What are the objectives of this SE content and pedagogy?

The paper is organized as follows. In the first part methodological approach, we propose a detailed regarding both data collection and Criteria, and action is taken, after this, a synthesis of background literature. In section 3, the findings and discussions are discussed. Section 4 presents Conclusion and Future research.

2. Research methodology

Since there has been so much study on SEE, it isn't easy to do a comprehensive literature review. The second choice is to use a narrative literature review, which has several drawbacks and has been heavily criticized. As a result, the current paper employs a systematic literature review to aid in a transparent and consistent literature review ^[7].

The search includes database SCOPUS and WEB OF SCIENCE in the time range between 2007 to January 2020. Moreover, to look at current practices in the curricula content and teaching methods in social entrepreneurship, we used the entrepreneurship, social entrepreneurship, and education journals. We used the phrases "social entrepreneurship education" in abstract/title/keywords, and "curriculum," "pedagogy," "content," and "methods in full text. The articles found were reviewed and downloaded into bibliographical software.

Figure N°1: Stages in SLR process

Source: own study

3. Literature review

It is essential to explain what we mean by social entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship education to discuss social entrepreneurship education.

3.1 Social entrepreneurship

Social entrepreneurship is a young concept that emerged in the 1990s on both sides of the Atlantic ^[8,9]. Likewise, many researchers confirm that the topic is generally accepted as being new in practice. Social entrepreneurship is not a new phenomenon, its language may be new, and its formulation is relatively recent^[10,11].

In reviewing the literature on this topic, we found that the origins and conceptions of this research theme have been treated from two approaches: an American approach that focuses more on the figure of the entrepreneur and a European approach that focuses more on certain specificities of the social enterprise^[12].

The American approach is composed of two schools of thought: (1) the school of market resources, which stipulates that a social enterprise is a private non-profit organization that uses market economic activities to service its social mission (Skloot, 1987; Young and Salamon, 2002). Work has followed this trend while expanding the scope to include a wide range of organizations, whether for-profit or not-for-profit, as long as they engage in market activity for a social purpose ^[13]. (2) The school of social innovation emphasizes the innovative nature of the social entrepreneur ^[14,15].

The European approach is mainly interested in social enterprise, also known as social and solidarity economy enterprises. Indeed, the EMES Network's work provided the first theoretical and empirical basis for a conceptualization of the European School of Social Enterprise ^[12].

Moreover, when one digs into the literature on the origins and history of social entrepreneurship, historical success stories and extreme examples of social entrepreneurship are cited by many authors, including those founders considered true predecessors in this field, notably a social enterprise called the "Grameen-Bank" initiated in 1976 by the inventor Muhammad Yunus. Insofar as the Grameen Bank of microcredit has changed the lives of millions of people by providing financial services to the poor, especially women^[8].

A second success story often cited in the academic landscape of the Ashoka Foundation, created by its founder Bill Drayton in 1980 to provide seed money for entrepreneurs with a social vision

[8]. It was one of the first organizations explicitly designed to fund social entrepreneurs, whose goal was to provide these entrepreneurs with the means to develop and the financial resources and professional network to disseminate their ideas and solutions.

3.2 Entrepreneurship education

Since the first entrepreneurship course was taught at Harvard Business School in 1947, entrepreneurship education (EE) programs in higher education have grown rapidly and globally [4,6,16–18]. This shows the significance of entrepreneurship in every society's economy. There is an implicit assumption that there is a correlation between providing EE and promised economic growth, job creation, and overall economic development.

In addition, there is a discussion between academics and business people whether it is possible to teach entrepreneurship^[19,20]. Some view entrepreneurship as a natural skill for which one is born and cannot be taught; however, this can also be said of other professionals, including engineering or medicine^[21]. Simultaneously with this debate, ^[21] proposed that to avoid stagnation of the research, the focus should shift from whether (EE) can be taught or not to the fundamental questions arising from education science: what, how, for whom, why, and for what outcomes is the EE program designed?, in addition, focusing on education science will lead to the development of successful (EE) programs that align with entrepreneurial learning practices [22,23].

Furthermore, there are several narrow and broad definitions of entrepreneurship education, both narrow and broad definitions ^[21,23]. And, each definition is taken from the definition of entrepreneurship itself. However, an agreement has been reached on two elements for understanding (EE): one is a broader definition that includes the acquisition of personal values, attitudes, behaviors, and skills for entrepreneurship, and the other is committed to practical preparation to launch the entrepreneurial (ad)venture ^[23,24].

Nevertheless, the content and educational methods for teaching entrepreneurship are as diverse as the definitions of (EE) ^[21,23,25,26]. As indicated by several authors ^[27–29] the development of entrepreneurship education is based on three main objectives: educating “about,” “for,” “in.

The first objective “about” is to develop an entrepreneurial culture among individuals, whether they are young or not, active or not active, men or women... The goal is to make these individuals more proactive in their lives in general. Thus, the objective goes far beyond the

framework of business creation: the spirit of the initiative must apply to both the personal and professional spheres ^[28].

The second objective “for,” is more focused on business creation. In this context, entrepreneurship training aims to inculcate the desire to create or take over a business (desirability) and to enable the individual to acquire skills in business creation (feasibility, measured for example, by the ability to do a market study or to draw up a business plan)^[30].

The third objective “in” is said to aim at making individuals become more entrepreneurial (innovative) in their existing firms or place of work^[20,29].

Some research questions the effectiveness of entrepreneurial education for economic or individual results ^[4,6]. It is also argued that entrepreneurship education needs further conceptual and theoretical development.

4. Results and discussions

This section contains two sub-sections: “Descriptive analysis” and “Content analysis.” The “Descriptive analysis” sub-section presents the following issues: papers over time, papers across journals, most used words, and prolific authors. The “Content analysis” shows different topics in this area.

4.1 Descriptive analysis

4.1.1 paper over time

As shown in Figure 2, the number of publications on social entrepreneurship education began to rise significantly from 2007 onward, with a peak in 2012 of 10 articles published. A large number of articles were published in 2012 (10 papers), 2019 (5 papers), an equal number of papers (2 papers) were published in 2011, 2013, 2014, and 2020.

The search also states that the majority of the articles were published from the years 2007-2012; the oldest documented research on social entrepreneurship education was conducted in 2002 by the ASHOKA foundation, which corresponds with the point made in the literature that social entrepreneurship education is a relatively new field

Figure N°2: Number of publications the papers over time

Source: own study

4.1.2 Papers across journals

Figure 3 lists the journals in which (SEE) research has been published in the last decade. This list informs us that (SEE) research has found its place in a variety of journals, the journal with the highest number of published articles on the topic of (SEE) were the journal “Academy of Management Learning & Education” (10 papers), Education + Training (2 papers), Journal of Knowledge Management (2 papers), Social Enterprise Journal (2 papers). The other journals published only one of our selected papers. However, most of the research was published in entrepreneurship journals. It implies that SEE is considered to be a practical discipline.

Figure N°3: Paper across journals

Source: own study

4.1.3 Most –used words

The "Nvivo" platform used to analyze words in the 30 publications selected, focusing on their titles and abstracts. This analysis verified that the words "entrepreneurship," "Students," "social," "education," "program," "business," and "entrepreneur" are significant and carry considerable weight in these publications.

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4.2.1 SEE curricula content

The syllabi content analysis is the standard framework for assessing the topics and pedagogical methods in universities' programs. The most discussed curricula content are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: SEE curricula content

<i>Study</i>	<i>Contents</i>
[33] [34]	SEE programs and courses need to be adapted around three crucial challenges facing social entrepreneurs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Managing accountability; - Manage the double bottom line; - Managing identity.
[35]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Addressing social needs or problems in ways that make a positive contribution to the community; - Opportunity recognition; - Innovation; - Scaling a social venture; - Resource acquisition to accomplish the mission of the organization; - Creating a sustainable business model; - Measuring outcomes.
[36]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Educating “about”: - Social opportunity specific knowledge. - Social venture specific knowledge. - Educating “for”: - Multiple logics bridging skills
[37]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The capacity to measure outcomes; - Problem solving; - Identify social opportunities; - Manage financial capital; - Create business plans, Innovate, create, and formulating strategies.
[38]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Defining SE; - Marketing; - Business models and plans; - Finance and fundraising; - Measuring and outcomes Management.
[39]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The history and contemporary issues of SE; - The biography of current social enterprises/entrepreneurs; - Resource-based theory; - The concept of bricolage and effectuation and ethical, social enterprise branding.
[40]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to social entrepreneurship, - Identification and evaluation of social opportunities, - Legal regulation of social entrepreneurship,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Dynamic business models,- Marketing research of the social products and services market,- Search for investment for the development of social enterprises,- Opening and registration of social enterprises,- Strategy of social development of the enterprises,- Measuring the social impact of enterprises,- Basics of accounting,- Business and financial management of social enterprises,- Business ethics and communication
[41].	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Understanding SE;- Enhancing the students' skill requirements academic;- Enterprises knowledge;- Entrepreneurial sense and administration of social enterprises.

Although entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship are now recognized as academic disciplines and fields of research, there is still much controversy and disagreement over the ideal content and curriculum of entrepreneurship programs. We see from the results above that social entrepreneurship education also contains various contents. At the same time, there is a lack of uniformity on "what" is taught, causing the courses to vary widely. These models represent a conceptual view of social entrepreneurship programs adopted by each institute.

Also, as it is inevitable that the course content will depend on the course objective, we will link the SEE content with its proposed goals in our grouping of different themes of SEE provision. Learning objectives of EE programs could range from the 'about' form concerns learning to understand entrepreneurship and knowledge building. The "for" relate to learning to become an entrepreneur, the "in" for making individuals become more entrepreneurial (innovative) in their existing firms or place of work. It is observed that SEE program objectives significantly impact the overall program delivery and design, including who delivers the courses.

4.2.2 Teaching Methods

Table 3: Teaching methods

Study	Teaching methods
[33]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weave social entrepreneurship topics, cases, and reading into traditional courses; - Develop social entrepreneurship speaker series; - Have students develop teaching cases based on real social enterprises; - Introduce social enterprise business plan assignment; - Introduce social enterprise consulting projects; - Provide opportunities for social enterprise internships.
[35]	<p>Various teaching methods in the development of a social entrepreneurship course.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conventional course; - Class discussions; - The case process; - Practical projects ranging from interviewing/shadowing social entrepreneurs in drafting a fictional social business plan; - Service/experiential learning projects (75% of the social enterprise faculty offer meaningful training for students through this pedagogy): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Social business plan for a social enterprise, ● Consulting with a social venture, ● Developing an earned income strategy for a social organization, ● Starting a social venture, ● Interning or writing a grant proposal for a social organization.
[42] [43]	<p>Many traditional techniques (i.e., Readings, lectures, and cases) can be tailored in educating SE, but incorporating group social entrepreneurship projects into their course curricula is the most effective mechanism for helping students builds identity through active engagement.</p>
[36]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Course discussions; - Guest speakers; - Internships; - Introducing students to the social sector through social work; - Exposure to different social workers; - Knowledge about different types of social institutions; - Taking public policy and social courses.
[44]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning-by-doing
[45]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service-learning
[39]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guest speakers/Networking; - Group comparative analysis of real social enterprise cases; - Teamwork on real social projects/presentations.
[46]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experiential learning projects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Action-research,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service learning - a "traditional" innovative social business plan;
[47],	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service-learning
[41]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Theory and history; - Case studies; - Group work and discussion; - Interviews, - Guest speakers; - Fieldwork; - Analytical methodology; - Business plans.

Another important field of research may be the teaching methods widely found in social entrepreneurship programs. Various learning techniques and approaches are deployed worldwide through various SEE programs. Classical educational methods are lectures, readings, workbook exercises, case-based class discussions, discussions with experts, guest speakers, individual coaching, and role plays. Most auteur confirms that Service/experiential learning projects and learning by doing are some of the most effective methods that have significant educational practice implications in social entrepreneurship education and that enable students to enhance their knowledge of social businesses [35,44,48].

The majority of the methods developed work through education "for" social entrepreneurship, rather than "about," which point that this educational field has taken a direct step towards action and experience-oriented teaching. Also, the methods used in social entrepreneurship education depend usually follow the evolution of the entrepreneurial goals.

5. Conclusion and future research

This paper aimed to contribute to mapping the curricula content and teaching methods in social entrepreneurship education programs. Our conclusion was built upon extensive articles published in social entrepreneurship education, including database SCOPUS and WEB OF SCIENCE in the time range between 2007 to January 2020.

The findings show that SEE programs contain different content and teaching methods, while there is a lack of uniformity on "what" and "how" taught social entrepreneurship. The result shows that the standard practices of SEE programs' content and teaching methods can be classified into three broad objectives.

The first objective makes extensive use of theoretical content. It is a teacher-centered teaching approach that teaches students "about" entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship, intending to raise students' understanding of entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship as a career option^[36]. The second and the third objectives, educating "for" and "in" entrepreneurship, target graduate business people and facilitating individuals to become more innovative in their existing place of work. They are more learner-centered than content-built. This is accomplished by either providing an atmosphere in which students can mimic real-life social projects or by allowing them to start or contribute to the development of social ventures. The literature tends more on these last two objectives.

Conscious of the relevance and interest of such a subject, it seems possible to explore multiple future researches. There is a scarcity of research on social entrepreneurship education and training initiatives developed outside of universities. In this light, future studies should explore this question of the public. SEE programs must be addressed to the different publics: such as women, unemployment...

There is a lack of agreement on the competencies and forms of skills students require^[49]. The social entrepreneurship curriculum covers a wide range of topics and methods built on numerous divergent theoretical assumptions. We believe that there is a lack of consistent theorizing in entrepreneurship education^[33]. In this context, when SE courses and teaching methods are properly aligned with outcomes and objectives, education will likely play a key role in encouraging and developing socially creative thinking responsible for social entrepreneurs^[39]. The research should break down the barriers between reflection and action,

academics and practice involved in social entrepreneurship education by adopting a critical and constructive attitude towards the issues and topics raised.

Another problem identified in the analysis of these articles is that there is little research on the impact and effectiveness of these social entrepreneurship education programs. Assessment is one of the essential facets of any educational program. SEE programs also involve evaluation^[35,50,51]. There are only two papers that deal with education "about" on social entrepreneurship. The first looked at high education students at the University of Tehran^[52], another paper assessed the degree of awareness of social entrepreneurship to Egyptian students'^[53]. Future research can explore the issues related to evaluating the impact of the program on social entrepreneurship education.

The research's practical effects mainly affect educators, trainers, and teachers working in social entrepreneurship education. They propose that the implementation of social entrepreneurship education programs be seen from new eyes. Entrepreneurial educators and instructors have to get knowledge about the standard practices in content and pedagogical situations.

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